

Book Review: Richards, J. C. with J. Pun. (2022). *Teaching and learning in English medium instruction: An introduction*. Routledge.**Yulia Kharchenko¹*****Maynooth University, Ireland***

Teaching and Learning in English Medium Instruction (2022) by Jack C. Richards with Jack Pun seeks to introduce the concepts and approaches to English medium instruction (EMI) to a new generation of EMI teachers and language teaching professionals. In under 300 pages of this accessible volume, the authors review key theories and research in EMI, discuss implications for teaching practice, and offer a variety of practical advice for EMI teachers. The wide appeal of this book is its advantage. Unlike other literature on EMI that focuses on specific education sectors, such as higher education (McKinley & Galloway, 2022) or specific geographical regions (Fenton-Smith et al., 2017; Henriksen et al., 2019), the volume applies broadly to secondary and higher education settings regardless of location. It provides a comprehensive overview of the issues of academic literacy and the challenges of teaching academic content through English, and it serves as a basis for critical reflection on the impact and consequences of EMI. The broad scope of the book means it is suitable for a variety of audiences, and the readers are invited to choose sections relevant to them.

The eleven chapters in the volume are organised into four parts, centred around key themes in EMI. Part 1, *Foundations of EMI*, includes three chapters that introduce the nature and the background of EMI. Part 2 focuses on the nature of academic literacy in EMI contexts and examines the linguistic dimensions of academic discourse that EMI educators need to be aware of. Part 3 is devoted to the impact of EMI on both teachers and students, the social capital students hope

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to derive from EMI and the challenges they face in doing so. Part 4 concludes the book with recommendations for professional development of EMI educators and suggests ways to evaluate EMI programs, using case studies of program evaluations.

The volume engages with the readers throughout. Each chapter finishes with a set of discussion questions, which help the readers review the ideas from the chapter and prime for the ideas in the coming sections. The discussion questions are followed by two or three practical follow-up activities designed to illustrate the points made in the chapter. For example, the readers are asked to write a country profile according to EMI typology presented in Chapter 3 or to analyse a textbook chapter to identify potential language difficulties for EMI students. Current and future EMI teachers, especially those without a language teaching background or knowledge, will benefit from these bite-sized tasks, which are illustrative of the challenges and specifics of teaching through the medium of English.

Chapter 1 presents a useful overview of the concept and history of English-medium instruction and discusses justifications used to support its implementation. Here, EMI as a format more common in tertiary level, is contrasted with other teaching approaches such as Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), English for Specific Purposes (ESP) and English for Academic Purposes (EAP). Chapter 2 distils the many contexts and features of EMI into a typology of EMI forms, adapted from the authors' previous work (Richards & Pun, 2021), which is helpful in comparing EMI across various settings. Chapter 3 presents key issues of EMI implementation in different contexts, including program design, student and teacher support, EMI program goals and implementation. Together, the first three chapters effectively set the overall scene of English-medium education and prepare the reader for the subsequent detailed and practical sections.

Discussing the nature of academic literacy in EMI, chapters 4 and 5 argue that it includes not merely the knowledge of concepts, ideas and theories. Academic literacy, which in this book is equated with discipline literacy, also involves the ability to participate in communicative practices of the discipline, using the appropriate genres and text types and being aware of its linguistic dimensions. Examples of disciplinary text types and their linguistic features, provided in Chapter 5, are especially practical for EMI teachers willing to apprentice their students into the academic discourse of the discipline. This part of the book also raises an important question about whose responsibility it is to teach the language while developing academic literacy. Various schools of thought on this are

reviewed. The authors conclude with an argument – one they return to throughout the book – that the distinction between teaching content and language is not achievable in practice. It is crucial for EMI teachers to develop an understanding of how language is used in their disciplines. The authors' own position is that EAP and subject teachers are jointly responsible for developing academic literacy in EMI settings.

Part 3 is arguably the most practical section of the book. It begins with the overview of EMI teacher characteristics in Chapter 6, and the subsequent chapters offer a wealth of practical strategies that EMI teachers can use to support their students. Chapter 7, *Teaching in EMI*, makes a convincing argument that teaching through the medium of English poses unique challenges and is distinct from teaching in one's first language (L1). The chapter draws on research to offer specific instructional strategies in EMI, including before, during and after teaching. This is complemented by a list of teacher-reported strategies in the appendix, which is a real-life snapshot of how EMI teachers support their students in learning both language and content. Chapter 8 discusses the nature of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) instruction and how it can be implemented to support EMI students. Chapter 9, *Learning in EMI*, is a counterpart to Chapter 7, written from the student perspective. It is of particular interest as it systematically outlines the challenges students may experience in EMI classrooms and then presents research-based options for EMI educators to support their students in developing discipline literacy. The suggested techniques could serve equally well as a foundation for EMI teacher development as well as a basis for personal reflection on one's teaching and teacher identity.

If there is one criticism of Chapters 7 and 9, it is the manner in which the authors position teachers' and students' use of L1 and translanguaging as "coping strategies". While acknowledging that teachers and students may see value in using L1 to deal with the demands of EMI teaching and learning, the suggested teaching strategies do not include using EMI learners' existing language repertoires. This is at odds with other EMI literature that emphasises planned multilingual approaches to teaching and learning (Lasagabaster, 2022; Sahan et al., 2022) and argues that the 'E' in EMI does not stand for English-only (Sahan & Rose, 2021).

The final part of the book covers the professional development of EMI educators and the evaluation of EMI programs. Chapter 10 examines two core domains of knowledge and practice: the teacher's use of English and their pedagogical

knowledge and practices. Once again, strategies for improving teachers' use of English are illustrated, and the authors return to their argument that collaboration between subjects and English teachers is beneficial in EMI professional development. Chapter 11 provides an overview of approaches to evaluating EMI programs, and Chapter 12 concludes the volume with a concise summary and recommendations for best practices in EMI.

Overall, the book provides an accessible introduction to EMI and a wealth of practical advice to EMI educators. Unlike a lot of EMI literature on the market, it does not present in-depth results of EMI research centred around a type of setting or geographical region, nor does it aim to do so. The book's notable strength is the broad scope of teaching and learning issues being covered. The authors find an effective balance between theory and practice and promote readers' engagement with key questions in EMI that have been raised in the scholarly community: what academic literacy in EMI is, whose responsibility it is to develop it, and what the best practice is in achieving this.

Given that the book aims to introduce key EMI concepts and discuss the many practical issues at classroom level, the overview is understandably broad rather than deep. For this reason, it may not be suitable for language education researchers looking for the latest research insights from specific EMI settings. However, for interested postgraduate students and current and future EMI teachers, the book can serve as an introduction to the considerable and fast-growing EMI literature devoted to more specific aspects of EMI.

This volume can be used as a coursebook in applied linguistics and TESOL programs with EMI specialisation. It will interest in-service EMI teachers and EAP and ESP teachers, especially in settings where collaboration between the two specialists is feasible. Teacher educators and professional development providers will also find the volume a useful, practical resource for developing the teaching practices of EMI teachers. Finally, the volume can be a sobering read for EMI policy developers as it critically and systematically unpacks the many challenges and consequences of implementing EMI.

AUTHOR

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